

Multivariate interaction analysis of maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotypes grown under different environmental conditions

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Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is an important staple crop that considerably contributes to global food and feed security. Since maize grain yield is a complex trait, breeders aim to improve both the yield and yield components. As one of the important yield components, the kernel row number (KRN) per ear, has a significantly positive effect on grain yield. Despite being a quantitative trait, it can be influenced by genotypes, environments and environment by genotype interactions (GEI). The objective of this study was to estimate the stability of three maize genotypes and evaluate the influence of GEI on the trait kernel row number per ear using the additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) model. The field trials were performed in ten different environments, control and four levels of nitrogen application (50, 100, 150 and 200 kg N ha⁻¹) in two growing seasons. The experimental design was set up according to the randomized complete block design with three replications. The analysis of variance of the AMMI model identified all sources of trial variation that were statistically significant. The proportions of the total variance in KNR in maize attributing to the environments contributed with 52.10 %, while genotypes contributed with 32.65 % and GEI contributed with 15.24 % to the total variation. Analysis of GEI using the Interaction Principal Components (IPCA) showed a statistical significance of the first main component, IPCA1 for KRN, which explained 88.03 % of the GEI variation. Observed significant mean squares for environment, genotype and GEI significantly influenced yield traits and revealed that maize genotypes responded differently to various nitrogen conditions. The present finding could be useful for optimal and rational use of fertilizers, as well as for the identification of maize genotypes with stable reactions across different environments for grain yield traits.